

Machine Learning versus Traditional Regression for Early Childhood Caries Risk Factor Identification: A Methodological Comparison Study

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Abstract

Aim: To compare traditional regression and machine learning approaches for identifying risk factors associated with early childhood caries (ECC) in Latvian preschool children.

Methods: This case-control study included 209 children aged 2 to 5 years (102 with ECC, 107 caries-free), with data collected in Latvia between 2020 and 2021. Traditional models included logistic and spline regression. ML models included random forest, XGBoost, elastic net, and k-nearest neighbours (KNN). Model discrimination was evaluated using AUC.

Results: Logistic regression achieved an AUC of 0.92. Spline regression achieved 0.93. ML models performed similarly: random forest (AUC = 0.92), XGBoost (0.91), elastic net (0.89), and KNN (0.86). Logistic regression identified visible plaque (OR = 9.14, 95% CI [4.08, 21.9]), infrequent parental brushing (OR = 5.13, 95% CI [1.73, 16.4]), and reduced toothbrushing frequency (OR = 3.49, 95% CI [1.47, 8.57]) as the strongest risk indicators. No ML model showed advantage over logistic regression.

Conclusions: ML did not outperform traditional regression in identifying ECC risk factors or improving clinical utility. Logistic regression remains a valid and interpretable method for ECC risk modelling in dental public health research.

Keywords: early childhood caries, machine learning, logistic regression, risk factors, predictive modelling, oral epidemiology

Introduction

Early childhood caries (ECC) affects almost half of preschool children globally (Uribe, Innes and Maldupa, 2021). In Latvia, caries prevalence in children exceeds the European average (Maldupa et al., 2021). Identifying risk factors is essential for developing prevention strategies. Logistic regression has been the standard approach for caries risk assessment. A systematic review found that standardised caries risk assessment models still have limited scientific evidence supporting their effectiveness (Cagetti et al., 2018).

Machine learning (ML) methods can handle non-linear relationships and high-dimensional data. A scoping review found that ML algorithms, particularly logistic regression and random forest, were the most frequently used methods for caries risk assessment (Bhatia et al., 2025). Some studies suggest ML outperforms traditional regression. Qu et al. (2022) found that random forest achieved an AUC of 0.91 compared to 0.86 for logistic regression in predicting ECC. Çiftçi and Aşantoğrol (2024) reported 95.8% accuracy for Multilayer Perceptron in adults.

However, comparisons have shown mixed results. Dey, Ogwo and Tellez (2024) found that traditional regression outperformed ML for permanent dentition caries. Wang et al. (2024) found high risk of bias across caries prediction models, with AUC values ranging from 0.57 to 0.91. Most studies have focused on prediction accuracy, while few have evaluated whether ML identifies different risk factors or provides better clinical utility than traditional regression. Evidence from Eastern European populations, where caries prevalence exceeds the European average and evidence-based prevention strategies are needed, is limited. And more importantly, whether ML methods offer practical advantages over simpler regression approaches for informing public health policy remains unclear. This study compared traditional regression and ML approaches for identifying ECC risk factors in Latvian preschool children.

Methods

Study design and setting

This was an ancillary analysis of a case-control study conducted in Latvia between September 2020 and December 2021. The parent study collected data on ECC risk factors in preschool children attending kindergartens across Latvia. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Riga Stradins University (Nr. 22-2/148/2021). Caregivers provided informed consent for their children's participation. The dataset has been previously published and is available at RSU Dataverse (DOI: 10.48510/FK2/PZL9DW).

Participants

The study included children aged 2 to 5 years attending kindergartens in Latvia. Cases were children with clinically diagnosed ECC according to the American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry definition: presence of one or more decayed, missing due to caries, or filled tooth surfaces in any primary tooth in a child under 6 years. Controls were children with intact dentition and no caries experience. Clinical examinations were performed by calibrated examiners.

The original dataset contained 237 observations with 15 variables. Missing data were present for breastfeeding duration (17.7%), parental brushing (11.0%), and mouth breathing (5.5%). After excluding observations with missing data on key predictors, 209 children remained for analysis (102 with ECC, 107 caries-free). The ECC prevalence in the analytical sample was 48.8%. The mean age was 3.4 years (range 2 to 5).

Variables

The outcome variable was ECC status (presence or absence), coded as a binary variable.

Predictor variables were selected based on established risk factors for ECC and included:

Demographic factors: Child age (continuous, in years) and sex (binary: boy or girl).

Oral hygiene behaviours: Toothbrushing frequency (categorical: twice daily or more, evenings only, less than daily or never), parental brushing assistance (categorical: every night, occasionally, seldom or never), and toothpaste type (categorical: fluoride, low fluoride, fluoride-free).

Dietary factors: Sugar-containing beverage consumption (binary: yes or no) and solid sugar intake (binary: yes or no).

Feeding practices: Bottle feeding (binary: yes or no) and breastfeeding duration (continuous, in months).

Clinical indicators: Visible plaque accumulation (binary: present or absent, assessed clinically) and mouth breathing (binary: yes or no, based on caregiver report and clinical observation).

Statistical analysis

Traditional regression models

We fitted a multivariable logistic regression model with all predictor variables entered simultaneously. Odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated using profile likelihood methods. Model fit was assessed using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). The logistic regression model achieved an AIC of 211 and BIC of 261.

We also fitted a spline regression model using natural cubic splines for continuous predictors (age, breastfeeding duration) to allow for non-linear relationships between these variables and the log-odds of ECC.

Machine learning models

We developed four ML models using the tidymodels framework in R (Kuhn and Wickham, 2020):

Random forest: An ensemble method that constructs multiple decision trees and aggregates their predictions. We tuned the number of trees (500 to 1500), minimum node size, and number of variables considered at each split.

XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting): A gradient boosting algorithm that builds trees sequentially, with each tree correcting errors from previous trees. We tuned the learning rate, tree depth, and number of boosting rounds.

Elastic net: A regularised logistic regression that combines L1 (lasso) and L2 (ridge) penalties. We tuned the mixture parameter (alpha) and regularisation strength (lambda).

K-nearest neighbours (KNN): A non-parametric method that classifies observations based on the majority class among the k closest training examples. We tuned the number of neighbours (k).

Data were randomly split into training (75%, n = 156) and test (25%, n = 53) sets with stratification by outcome to maintain similar ECC prevalence in both sets. The test set contained 27 caries-free and 26 children with ECC. Hyperparameter tuning was performed using 10-fold cross-validation on the training set. Final models were evaluated on the held-out test set.

Model evaluation

Model discrimination was assessed using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC). AUC values range from 0.5 (no discrimination) to 1.0 (perfect discrimination). We considered AUC differences of less than 0.01 as equivalent performance, following recommendations for comparing prediction models (DeLong, DeLong and Clarke-Pearson, 1988).

Clinical utility was assessed through threshold analysis. For each model, we calculated sensitivity (proportion of ECC cases correctly identified) and specificity (proportion of caries-free children correctly identified) at risk thresholds from 0.3 to 0.7. The Youden index (sensitivity + specificity - 1) was computed to identify optimal classification thresholds. Higher Youden indices indicate better overall classification performance.

All analyses were conducted in R version 4.3 (R Core Team, 2023). The analysis followed the TRIPOD (Transparent Reporting of a multivariable prediction model for Individual Prognosis or Diagnosis) guidelines for reporting prediction model studies (Collins et al., 2015).

Results

Model discrimination

Table 1 shows the AUC values for all models. Spline regression achieved the highest AUC (0.93), followed by random forest and logistic regression (both 0.92). XGBoost achieved 0.91, elastic net 0.89, and KNN 0.86. No ML model achieved a higher AUC than logistic regression.

Table 1. Model discrimination performance (AUC)

Model	AUC	Difference vs Logistic Regression
Spline regression	0.93	+0.01
Random forest	0.92	0.00
Logistic regression	0.92	Reference
XGBoost	0.91	-0.01
Elastic net	0.89	-0.03
K-nearest neighbours	0.86	-0.06

Risk factors from logistic regression

Table 2 shows the logistic regression results. Visible plaque showed the strongest association (OR = 9.14, 95% CI [4.08, 21.9], $p < 0.001$). Children whose parents seldom or never assisted with brushing had higher odds of ECC (OR = 5.13, 95% CI [1.73, 16.4], $p = 0.004$). Reduced toothbrushing frequency was also associated with ECC: brushing in evenings only (OR = 3.49, 95% CI [1.47, 8.57], $p = 0.005$) and brushing less than daily (OR = 3.91, 95% CI [1.25, 13.4], $p = 0.023$).

Younger age was associated with higher ECC risk (OR = 0.67 per year, 95% CI [0.49, 0.89], $p = 0.007$). Longer breastfeeding duration was associated with increased ECC (OR = 1.06 per month, 95% CI [1.01, 1.12], $p = 0.023$). Sex, toothpaste type, sugar consumption, bottle feeding, and mouth breathing were not associated with ECC.

Table 2. Logistic regression results for ECC risk factors (n = 209)

Variable	OR	95% CI	p-value
Age (per year)	0.67	0.49, 0.89	0.007
Female (vs male)	0.72	0.33, 1.57	0.4
Parental brushing: occasionally	1.14	0.47, 2.69	0.8
Parental brushing: seldom/never	5.13	1.73, 16.4	0.004
Visible plaque	9.14	4.08, 21.9	<0.001
Toothbrushing: evenings only	3.49	1.47, 8.57	0.005
Toothbrushing: less than daily	3.91	1.25, 13.4	0.023
Breastfeeding (per month)	1.06	1.01, 1.12	0.023

OR = odds ratio. CI = confidence interval. Reference categories: male, parental brushing every night, twice daily toothbrushing.

Clinical utility

At a 0.5 threshold, logistic regression achieved sensitivity 0.81 and specificity 0.82 (Youden index = 0.62). Random forest achieved similar values (sensitivity 0.85, specificity 0.85, Youden = 0.70). The optimal threshold for logistic regression was 0.4 (sensitivity 0.92, specificity 0.82, Youden = 0.74). No ML model showed a clear advantage over logistic regression across thresholds.

Discussion

ML methods did not outperform traditional logistic regression for identifying ECC risk factors in Latvian preschool children. Logistic regression achieved an AUC of 0.92, equivalent to or higher than all ML models tested. The risk factors identified are consistent with established evidence and directly interpretable for clinical practice.

Comparison with previous studies

Our findings contrast with studies reporting ML superiority. Qu et al. (2022) found random forest achieved an AUC of 0.91 compared to 0.86 for logistic regression in Chinese children. Çiftçi and Aşantoğrol (2024) reported 95.8% accuracy for Multilayer Perceptron in Turkish adults. Hasan et al. (2025) reported an AUC of 0.77 for random forest predicting ECC in Bangladeshi children.

However, our results align with other comparisons. Dey, Ogwo and Tellez (2024) found that traditional regression outperformed ML for permanent dentition caries. Wang et al. (2024) found that combined predictive models achieved an AUC of 0.79, comparable to our logistic

regression. The discrepancy may reflect sample size differences. Our sample was small ($n = 209$), which may limit the advantage of ML methods.

Risk factors identified

Logistic regression identified visible plaque, infrequent parental brushing, and reduced toothbrushing frequency as the strongest risk indicators. Hasan et al. (2025) similarly found dental plaque as the strongest predictor of ECC. Qu et al. (2022) identified parental monitoring of brushing among their top predictors. The association between younger age and higher ECC risk likely reflects a cumulative exposure effect.

Implications for practice

Traditional logistic regression remains a valid approach for ECC risk factor identification. It provides interpretable odds ratios for clinicians and policymakers. As Cagetti et al. (2018) noted, the scientific evidence for standardised caries risk assessment models remains limited. Our findings suggest that simpler regression approaches perform comparably to complex ML methods for population-level risk factor identification.

Limitations

The sample size was small ($n = 209$), which may have limited ML performance. The test set contained only 53 observations. The cross-sectional design prevents establishing temporal relationships.

Conclusions

ML did not outperform traditional logistic regression for identifying ECC risk factors in this Latvian sample. Logistic regression achieved equivalent discrimination ($AUC = 0.92$) and identified clinically relevant risk factors: visible plaque, infrequent parental brushing, and reduced toothbrushing frequency. Traditional regression methods remain valid for ECC risk modelling in dental public health research.

Declarations

Ethics approval: RSU Ethics Committee Nr. 22-2/148/2021. Caregivers provided informed consent.

Data availability: RSU Dataverse (DOI: 10.48510/FK2/PZL9DW).

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Conflicts of interest: None declared.

Author contributions: SEU designed the study, performed analysis, and wrote the manuscript. JG participated in data collection and data preparation. IM participated in study design and revised the manuscript. All authors approved the final version.

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